

HΣPHÆSTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new tecHnologies in crAft for
prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS

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Establishment of a network on craft

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The Report is a document which evolves during the lifespan of the project and registers all relevant changes in the life cycle of the HEPHAESTUS project. This document will be updated with more information about the network in the last month of the project.

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About HEPHAESTUS

Working across the **regional craft ecosystems** of **Bassano del Grappa (IT)**, **Bornholm (DK)**, **Dals Långed (SE)**, and **Venice (IT)**, the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is *to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable*. HEPHAESTUS will **test and evaluate solutions** co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a “**Future of Craft**” **Green Living Lab** situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a **sustainable network** (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long- lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

Objective 1: Develop new **sustainable business models** for the craft sectors.

Objective 2: Combine **cutting-edge technologies** with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.

Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of **craft in the future**, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.

Objective 4: Develop a **lifelong learning methodology** and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.

Objective 5: Establish a **Green Living Lab** for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.

Objective 6: To design and operationalise a **bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation** strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. . A unique value added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

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1. Executive Summary

This report highlights the project team's objectives, activities, and accomplishments in order to develop, enhance, and solidify the notion of an arts and crafts ecosystem throughout Europe.

It then reveals, from a programmatic standpoint, the goals driving the creation of a craft-based network, as well as the main outcomes achieved by the Hephæstus consortium in involving as many partners, stakeholders, and policymakers as possible through territorial dissemination actions and broader digital storytelling and web communication activities.

It then outlines not only the aims, but also the achievements accomplished via the engagement of many types of stakeholders, exhibiting the formation of a genuine network for the development of craft-based territorial cultural ecosystems.

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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2. Core concepts

The Hephæstus project aims to strengthen artisanal activity as both a material heritage (tools and raw materials) and an intangible legacy (knowledge and skills), which have been a fundamental value for ages. As a result, the project aspires to build on a European perspective that sees cultural and creative industries as a driver of growth, capable of meeting the difficulties of the triple transition: social, digital, and green.

The New European Bauhaus (NEB) represents a watershed moment in the European economy's transformation, with cultural and creative industries (CCIs) being called upon to take the lead in guiding traditional industries and SMEs through a process of adopting new technologies, new ways of designing based on the use of sustainable and recyclable materials, and increased awareness about the planet and biodiversity.

In this context, arts and crafts in Europe are at a crossroads: while traditional crafts are gradually fading (as in the Venice ecosystem), contemporary public education systems are eager to upgrade to incorporate crafts as a generator of new creative business. New digital technologies, led by FabLab's, for example, offer potential hitherto unknown for more conventional artists, while the problems of innovation focus on the digitalization of objects and archives.

The Hephæstus project is based on two main principles:

1. The New European Bauhaus's core principles allow for the creation of bridges between disciplines, foster sustainable approaches, and steer the transformation of craft ecosystems along three values: sustainability (circularity, zero pollution, and biodiversity preservation), aesthetics (quality objects, quality experiences) and inclusion (diversity, accessibility, affordability).
2. Creative economy and entrepreneurship: cross-innovation between creative and craft-industrial elements, as well as the possibility to establish training and life-long learning programmes, are intended to promote the creation of new creative entrepreneurship in the territories of action research.

To put these concepts into reality, the consortium will host a series of workshops across all WPs to involve craft-makers, key stakeholders, and cultural and creative enterprises, assuring project commitment and effective communication and dissemination.

The project members will lead a craft-driven innovation process to establish the Living Lab on Bornholm. The project aims indeed to innovate craft and contribute to the experience economy, particularly focusing on sustainable tourism and waste management through the circular economy concept. Hephæstus' transformative approach remains profoundly participatory and transdisciplinary: the entire project involves taking action on the ground, researching the environment for innovation, and sharing perspectives with select audiences.

3. Creating sustainable craft-technology relationships

Hephæstus aims to foster long-term craft-technology partnerships by connecting research and historic sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, regional and national authorities, companies, and other stakeholders.

This will be done through dissemination and communication activities created in the four craft ecosystems (Venice, Bassano del Grappa, Dals Långed, and Fengersfors, Bornholm), as well as particular networking activities inside the Living Lab being set up in Bornholm.

Fablabs will play an important part in this operation because of the unique nature of their business model, which requires them to network and share information and technology.

Furthermore, through the establishment of museum archives dedicated to handicrafts, the project intends to foster a deeper appreciation of legacy and make craftspeople more aware of the value of new technologies in promoting handicraft production and preserving information that might otherwise be lost due to generational shift.

Throughout the length of the project, all events and conferences planned by the partners will encourage innovation, jobs, and sustainable growth; connect and integrate cultural and creative businesses with craft enterprises; promote new sustainable heritage tourism frameworks (e.g. Slow Tourism).

Project communication as a whole will operationalize these aims more effectively, depending on narrative to explain outcomes, involve the public and other stakeholders, and distribute project findings (via Craft Histories, for example). Through fieldwork and numerous workshops offered by the WPs, we will exhibit cross-border co-production of works and link craftsmen across their ecosystems.

The following sections provide a recap of all the dissemination and networking activities undergone by the project partners.

3.1. The workshop at *Salone dell'Alto Artigianato, Venice*

On September 30th 2023, Ca' Foscari University (UNIVE) organized an event as part of the Salone dell'Alto Artigianato Veneziano, the Municipality of Venice's inaugural craft fair. The event was organised in collaboration with the project partner Fablab Venezia, who welcomed us in their display space within the Salone (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Hephæstus event at the Salone Alto Artigianato in Venice

We gathered crafters and presented the Hephæstus project to the public, collaborating with the University of Rome Tor Vergata (UTOV) and the University of Gothenburg (UGOT). As part of the event, the D20 Art Lab artists' video "*Atmospheres of Craft*" was screened in the presence of artist Raffaella Rivi, followed by an open discussion with academics, artisans, and civil society about the issues raised in the video, particularly those relating to the Venice ecosystem (Figure 2). The session was also a unique chance for Fablab Venice to highlight the digital technology prospects for the arts and crafts industry.

Figure 2 – "*Atmospheres of Craft*" screening, 30th September 2023

4. Encouraging communities of practices for craftmakers

Hephæstus aims to foster long-term links and networks among research and heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, regional and national authorities, companies, and other stakeholders, promoting innovation, jobs, and sustainable growth. The resulting network of towns, heritage sites, businesses and museums will also contribute to the Living Lab's construction and operation. This will allow for the formation of communities of practice for craft-makers, cultural and creative industries, and Fablabs across sectors, including arts and culture, funders and the voluntary sector, academia, and policy. The intended goal is to facilitate occasions for people to meet, appreciate each other's points of view, acknowledge mutual concerns, agree on shared evidence, develop a shared sense of purpose and agree on the interventions to be implemented across the cultural and craft sectors.

The following subsections summarise the events the project's partners organised to build and strengthen the connections between the involved communities.

4.1. The focus group in Bassano del Grappa

On June 28th, 2023, Ca' Foscari University of Venice (UNIVE) conducted a focus group in Bassano del Grappa (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - Focus group in Bassano del Grappa, 8th June 2023

The goal was twofold: to conclude the D20 Art Lab exhibition "Atmospheres of Craft" at the Palazzo Sturm Museum, which had been inaugurated a month earlier during the Hephæstus kick-off meeting, and to encourage artisans to reflect on the system of relationships in the area, providing researchers with useful hints for the first interviews for the fieldwork in WP1. These synergies across work packages should be regarded one of the project's winning

keys, as well as the attunement between the consortium's many partners. Copenhagen Business School (CBS) proposed the focus group approach, which was then readapted by the Ca' Foscari University team.

Several craft-makers, scholars, and policymakers from the Municipality of Bassano del Grappa (CDBG) attended the event, which was hosted in the Museum's halls. The artisans were separated into two groups, directed by the two research teams, and asked to sketch on a map the important linkages in their value chain (customers, stakeholders, value system, etc.) (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Collaborative mapping session

The result was a common picture of what was happening in the Bassano del Grappa craftsmanship ecosystem, its supply chain and key needs, as well as a strengthening of the craft-makers' interpersonal relationships. In this sense, network development also entails sharing moments and activities, and developing communities of practice is crucial to rekindling a feeling of community and social cohesiveness.

4.2. The workshop “Crafting Craft Histories” in Venice

Ca' Foscari University of Venice (UNIVE) arranged a two-day in-depth study (December 14th and 15th 2023) named "*Crafting Craft Histories*" on the topic of craft histories, which corresponds to the contents of the associated deliverable D6.2. The event sought to leverage cooperation with Copenhagen Business School (CBS) as part of CBS students' visit to Venice for their *Philosophical Analysis in Business Studies* course. During the month of November, the Ca' Foscari University team prepared a collaborative Research Protocol with CBS and invited 5 craftswomen from Venice to participate in a first round of online interviews to share their business model, with an emphasis on their value proposition. On December 14th, the students, along by UNIVE researchers, paid visits to the interviewed artists' workplaces and conducted a second interview (Figure 5).

Figure 5 - Student outlining the interview main questions

The phase began with an in-person meeting at CBS headquarters in Copenhagen. UNIVE demonstrated the shooting and narrative process behind the creation of an effective short film (the Craft Histories, which will be released on the Hephæstus website). The lesson was then put into action during a visit to the artisan workshops, where students captured images and video recordings (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - Two crafters' studios

On December 15th, the students worked on video editing before giving a public presentation on the business model canvas of the assessed artisan companies. The workshop was attended by academics, students, and crafters who praised the CBS students' work and corroborated their findings. During the event, the D20 Art Lab artists were also present, and their movie "Atmospheres of Craft" was shown. Finally, the participants worked in groups to create posters summarizing their observations and comments on the Venice craft environment (Figure 7).

Figure 7 – Final day summary poster

4.3. The workshops in Göteborg and the future Symposium

The University of Goteborg (UGOT) arranged a local launch workshop at Dals Långed on August 24th and 25th. The kick-off programme began with a meet-up "fika" (coffee and cakes) at Studio Växt, a local co-working space in central Dals Långed where several of the Swedish Craft Ambassadors have membership. They showed their workplace and what they do, and after the TOUR-DE-WORKSHOP, UGOT organised a focus group with a collaborative mapping activity. The crafts ambassadors identified obstacles and opportunities for sustainable craft development in the local ecosystem of Dals Långed/Fengersfors.

Figure 8 - Collaborative mapping activity in Dals Långed

After the session, split into two teams, the group reconvened and presented their results to one another. After lunch, the UGOT team and the craft-makers conducted a collective bicycle tour in Dals Långed, utilizing a bike-sharing system (Cykla Gul) devised by one of the craft-makers (Figure 9). They went to Open Wood, a circular-economy-focused Fab lab, and then car-shared to Fengersfors, which is approximately a 20-minute drive from downtown. They continued with a second round of TOUR-DE-WORKSHOP, visiting the Not Quite (Lova and Jockum) and Strands workshop, a recently-founded collective space (Figure 10). The day ended by watching D20 Art Lab film together (the Dals Långed movie in focus), having follow-up discussions, and preparing and eating dinner together.

Figure 9 - Cykla Gul bikes

Figure 10 – Dals Långed ambassador during the workshop

Over the course of two days, UGOT strengthened its relationship with the craft-makers, fostering a culture of sharing and cooperation.

The University of Goteborg (UGOT) organized many other events in order to engage craft-makers and promote the project within the Swedish ecosystem. On November 29th a lecture about the theme of “Craft as consolation” by Copenhagen Business School was held in Dals Långed and on the 30th it was organized a workshop with the craft ambassadors during which they worked with paper while talking together and then discussed about their desires and goals to reach through the project (Figure 11).

Figure 11 – The workshop discussion

A third workshop with craft ambassadors in Sweden has been organized on the 7th and 8th of March 2024 with a focus on speculating on the future of craft. A manifesto produced in collaboration with Chat GPT was drafted during the event, and three workshops were outlined: one on the future of education, one on co-creation and a third one with a focus on gender.

UGOT also arranged several conferences and Research Days at the Academy of Art and Design, during which the professors involved in the project presented to the students their research on the careers of artisans and how they make a living. In addition, the institution presented the collaborative approach it relied on when working with craft ambassadors.

UGOT is also currently collaborating with the Craft Biennial of Crafts of Western Sweden to organize a conference on the economy and organization of crafts from May 2nd to the 6th.

Scholars and practitioners will participate to a two-day traveling symposium in western Sweden to offer their perspectives on craft, its economy and organization. Policies such as the European Union's New European Bauhaus and Sweden's Gestaltad Livsmiljö (Policy for the Designed Living Environment) emphasize indeed the importance of crafts and other forms of creative work, such as art, design, and architecture, in the development of a sustainable environment and an inclusive society. The conference will thus explore the economics and organisation of craft as critical challenges for both the sector and society as a whole. Crafters will play an important role in promoting new ideas as well as exchanging know-how and knowledge. In addition, UGOT offered them the option to exhibit their products in the Gothenburg Museum of Design over the same time period.

5. Establishing a craft-driven sustainable NEB cluster.

Hephaestus is also dedicated to the establishment of a craft-driven, sustainable NEB cluster or, in other words, a networking space to connect researchers, craftspeople, enterprises and business innovators in order to bring new products and services to market. The network will also be a valuable space to train for new technologies, to combine traditional and new skills, and for entrepreneurship to develop effective business plans. The cluster will be introduced in the consortium partners' instructional activities first, followed by our university partners. Hephæstus redefines craft as a cultural and creative industry, emphasizing its significance in shaping European identity and cultural legacy. The continuous involvement with associations, people, and economic sectors through workshops, residencies, and citizen labs arranged by the project contributes to a sense of belonging.

The NEB cluster also represent a valuable occasion to highlight the value of arts and crafts as green changemaker celebrating craft's vital position as a driver of sustainable innovation. Given the creative industries' ability to influence citizen behaviour, establishing a green craft-driven Bauhaus represents a promising threshold to transform green transitioning into appealing experiences, with the potential to significantly reshape consumer culture in a sustainable direction. While shifting craftsmanship into the circular economy through improved resource usage is crucial, the role of craft-makers as inspirators, introducing new ideals, experiences, and tales, has the potential to have a far-reaching influence.

Subsection 5.1 and 5.2 record the two events directed toward the establishment of the NEB cluster.

5.1. The kick-off meeting in Venice and Bassano del Grappa

Ca' Foscari University (UNIVE) had a kick-off meeting for the Hephæstus project on May 25th and 26th, 2023 in Venice and May 27th in Bassano del Grappa.

On May 25th, the project Steering Committee met to outline the next stages in establishing the work of the various task packages. On May 26th, an academic symposium on craft challenges was conducted at the Venice School of Management in Venice, attended by experts from across the world (Figure 12).

Figure 12 – Kick-off event at the Venice School of Management

On May 27th, a meeting was conducted to introduce the public to the Craft Ambassadors initiative, which was chosen to represent the ecosystems of Venice, Bassano, Dals Långed, and Bornholm. In the afternoon, the D20 Art Lab show "Atmospheres of Craft" was inaugurated in front of academics, students, craftsmen, policymakers, and members of the public (Figure 13).

Figure 13 – “Atmosphere of Craft” opening in Bassano del Grappa

5.2. The workshop in Bornholm

On August 15th, 2023, BOFA organised a workshop to establish the Living Lab at the BOFA implant in Rønne. The event featured presentations by Hephæstus and the Green Living Lab, as well as the D20 movie *"Atmospheres of Craft."* Following the presentation, the attendees were separated into two groups and invited to explore the difficulties and aspirations of the craft industry in Bornholm. One group was mostly made up of craftspeople, while the other was made up of stakeholders. The study team (CBS, UNIVE) randomly split amongst the tables. Participants used sheets, schemes, and stickers to map challenges related to competencies, new technologies, financial funding, cooperation, and sustainability. They then discussed expectations for the Living Lab and Hephæstus, as well as the benefits and drawbacks of participating in Bornholm's craft ecosystem (Figure 14).

At the conclusion of the session, BOFA suggested a tour of the waste management implant as it presents a unique feature: it allows individuals to scavenge and reuse previously discarded things (possibility limited to not dangerous waste and that does not require any specialised treatment).

Figure 14 – Concept map making in Rønne

6. Extending and maximising the impact

The goal of network building is to reach as many artisans as possible within the chosen ecosystems and to raise awareness of the craft ecosystem of the issues underlying the project. To achieve this challenge, we present two techniques:

- Firstly, we included some craftmakers during the first stage of project drafting and trial work that took place in 2021 and 2022 (especially in the workshop in Venice and Bassano in February 2022). In addition to the apparent goal of enabling data and information retrieval, the link with these parties served as a mean to include important stakeholders in the development of the research protocol, ensuring it addressed the crafters' actual challenges.
- Secondly, we leverage craftmakers' associations to reach their peers and members of their professional network. In this context, the role of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and craft associations, such as Confindustria and Confartigianato in Italy, DKoD in Denmark, and Svenska Slöjdföreningen-Svensk Form in Sweden, is crucial within the Hephaestus network. We are closely collaborating with craftmakers, as well as other relevant parties on a local level, to connect with existing professional networks.

Regarding the distribution strategy of project results, knowledge, products, and their application, as key indicator of the project success, will be mindful of:

- Making the projects' notions and findings accessible to all audiences, including non-professionals;
- Identifying various professional stakeholders who may become "research users", i.e. who may find the research results useful in developing the issues of arts and crafts on a local scale;
- Combining communication styles and strategies to increase awareness;
- Explaining how to retain social, personal, and cultural memory and knowledge allows for the symbolic expression of self-identity.

The communication and stakeholder involvement process is ongoing and iterative. Stakeholders are active collaborators in determining programme priorities, rather than passive recipients of study results. Numerous communication activities have been developed to provide a two-way, dynamic, and creative communication process. In this sense, the workshops we organized functioned as platforms for co-creation, testing, dissemination and sharing (Figure 15).

Implementing an iterative process with IMPACT in mind

Figure 15 – Hephæstus iterative project toward impact

The dissemination strategies will be specific about the ties between the research and dissemination processes, with a focus on the links between the project's outputs and the dissemination instruments, as well as the links between these tools and possible consumers of the project's findings. The results will be disseminated to craft ecosystem policymakers, craftmakers, technology providers, international academic communities, citizens, and civil society as a whole in order to raise awareness and knowledge about craft heritage and its critical contributions to the construction of European cultural identities (Figure 16).

Figure 16 – Hephæstus' intended outputs

Hephæstus' effect will grow with the development of the ecosystems' networks. The intended benefits for the networks are threefold:

1. The study intend to help politicians and craftspeople to engage more effectively within the ecosystems. It will be crucial in both gaining a better knowledge of the causes driving the KPIs and ensuring that craft groups effectively participate to local economic development decision making;

2. Thanks to the project's varied geographic composition, stakeholders can learn from the experiences of the other craft ecosystems while also establishing European relationships and networks that will persist beyond the project's duration;
3. The network between artisans and researchers will help to disseminate the study findings by transferring expertise and information collected in one site to others within the overall project and to a larger audience. Each consortium member will collaborate closely with the host stakeholders – especially cultural and creative industries, cultural institutions, craft associations and the general public – to identify requirements, communicate policy-relevant data from their unit with the rest of the team, and report back to their own unit on key policy developments in the project. A key role in the process will be played by the Green Living Lab, which will serve as an incubator for individuals to interact and learn from their experiences. The overarching aim is to engage and disseminate research knowledge at varying depths through distinct levels of participation: the findings will be translated into accessible formats to inform non-academic bodies to support, sustain, and develop the craft sector. Key documents to disseminate are policy briefs, or project deliverables on published arts and crafts issues to help policy makers investigate crucial aspects of sector policymaking.

The following subsections indicate the initial occasions through which the project's members are disseminating the initial findings and reaching the intended communities.

6.1. Academic conferences and presentations

The project's academic consortium has attended conferences and seminars to discuss craft-related themes and promote Hephæstus abroad. The conferences include EGOS, EURAM, FLITe Research Group, AOM, the Kyoto and OS workshop, as well as craft-related events and symposia in Denmark, Sweden and Italy (Figure 17).

Figure 17 – Hephaestus' scholars in conferences and events

Representatives from the Hephæstus community interacted with other European initiatives, including MOSAIC, Tracks4Craft, and Cultural Heritage 2.0, to share thoughts and perspectives and develop collaboration (Figure 18).

Figure 18 – Sharing thoughts and perspectives with other European initiatives

6.2. The meetings with the craft associations in Venice and Bassano

On January 16th and 25th, and February 2nd, 5th and 6th, Ca' Foscari University (UNIVE) organized meetings with leading craft associations (Confartigianato Venezia, CNA Venezia, Confartigianato Vicenza and CAN Veneto Ovest) (Figure 19).

Figure 19 – Ca' Foscari University meeting with craft associations' representatives

During these meetings, the partners (Ca' Foscari University, University of Rome Tor Vergata, Copenhagen Business School, Fablab Venice, and Bassano del Grappa Municipality) shared the next project steps with the craft associations and asked for their cooperation in sharing the questionnaire developed by UTOV for WP4, extracting data related to ATECO/NACE codes of crafts for UNIVE activities related to WP6, finding synergies for programmes and projects related to WP2, WP3, and WP5 activities.

Again, by using the different work packages as communication tools, we built valuable connections to maximize the consortium's efforts.

6.3. Students' involvement

On October 23rd, 2023, Marta Gasparin (Copenhagen Business School), Martin Quinn (Lancaster University), Steven Brown (Otto Monsted Visiting Professor at CBS), and Enrico Macciò (CBS) taught CBS students on the sociology of organisations. The team applied experiential learning techniques to create a business game based on the Hephæstus project, set in the thriving Danish ecosystem (Figure 20). The students worked in teams, each representing a different organization within the craft ecosystem, providing them with practical experience in real-world dynamics, teamwork, and strategy.

Figure 20 – Students collaborating in CBS

7. The Hephaestus network

During the first 12 months, the Hephaestus project team organized numerous events, workshops, and conferences, broadly disseminating the project's own key principles. So far, more than 210 craftmakers have been involved in the different events and more than 270 artisans during scientific activities, visits to dedicated fairs, and fieldwork. More than 42 representatives of craft associations have met, and about 66 entrepreneurs mainly belonging to the cultural and creative industries. An average of 80 academics and researchers per institution were involved and met, 20 policy makers from different ecosystems and about 740 people from the general public. The Hephaestus team also met with 3 representatives of other European projects, with whom experiences and recommendations were shared. We also connected with about 41 museums and cultural institutions and 11 craft-related festivals and associations. The details of the network activated by the various partners are described in the following tables (from Table 1 to Table 7).

NETWORK	UNIVE
ACADEMICS	Students
	Researchers
	Professors
MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS	Ministero della Cultura
	Direzione Regionale Musei Veneto
	Ateneo Veneto
	Fondazione Musei Civici
	Museo M9
	Museo di Palazzo Grimani
	Museo d'arte orientale Venezia
	Istituto Romeno di Cultura e Ricerca Umanistica
	Fondazione Ca' Foscari
The Solomon R. Guggenheim Foundation	
FESTIVALS AND ASSOCIATIONS	Festival Città Impresa Vicenza
OTHER CREATIVE INDUSTRIES	Nove terra di Ceramica
	Venezia da Vivere
	CREA Venice
	Lineadacqua edizioni
	La Piccionaia
CRAFT ASSOCIATIONS	Cabiria
	Confartigianato Venezia
	CNA Venezia
	Confartigianato Vicenza
SMEs	CNA Veneto Ovest
	Venezia FC
	Terra Sud
	Gruppo Montenegro
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	Ambrosetti
	Istituto Veneto per il Lavoro
POLICY MAKERS	Liceo De Fabris, Bassano
	Regione Veneto
	Comune di Venezia
	Comune di Bassano
CRAFTMAKERS	Comune di Vicenza
	Fieldwork, workshop, events, focus group

Table 1 - The network activated by UNIVE

NETWORK	CDBG
ACADEMICS	Researchers Professors
MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS	Museo di Palazzo Sturm Musei Civici di Bassano Fondazione Roi (Vicenza)
FESTIVALS AND ASSOCIATIONS	Operaestate festival Veneto, Bassano
CRAFT ASSOCIATIONS	Confartigianato Vicenza CNA Veneto Ovest AICC, associazione Italiana Città della Ceramica
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	Liceo De Fabris, Bassano
POLICY MAKERS	Comune di Nove
CRAFTMAKERS	Craft Ambassadors

Table 2 - The network activated by CDBG

NETWORK	BOFA
ACADEMICS	Researchers Professors Students
MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS	Hjorts Fabrik Makers Island Bornholms Museum of Art Centre for Regional & Tourism Research The Regional Municipality of Bornholm Bornholms Center for Crafts Anneberg Kulturpark
FESTIVALS AND ASSOCIATIONS	Bornholms Craft Week
CRAFT ASSOCIATIONS	Arts and Craft Association Bornholm
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	The Royal Academy of Glass and Ceramics
POLICY MAKERS	Bornholm Vice Mayor
CRAFTMAKERS	Workshop, field work, focus group, coffee meetings, varnishings, craft ambassadors

Table 3 - The network activated by BOFA

NETWORK	UGOT
ACADEMICS	Students
	Researchers
	Professors
MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS	Röhsska Museum of Design and Craft
	Halmens Hus
	Not Quite artists' collective
	Municipality of Bengtsfors
	Municipality of Gothenburg, Culture
	West Sweden Region, Culture
	Centre for Artistic Craft
	Kulturakademi (lifelong learning)
FESTIVALS AND ASSOCIATIONS	Craft Days in West Sweden
	Swedish Form (lobby organization)
	Science Festival in Gothenburg
	Furniture Fair in Stockholm
OTHER CREATIVE INDUSTRIES	Mötesplats Steneby
	Studio Växt (creative co-working space)
	Not Quite artists' collective
CRAFT ASSOCIATIONS	Swedish Centre for Artistic Craft
SMEs	Swedish Wood (Svensk-trä; Furniture industry)
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	Academy of Art and Design, Gothenburg
	School of Craft, Steneby
POLICY MAKERS	West Sweden Region
	Municipality of Gothenburg
	Swedish Arts Grant Committee
	Nämnden för Hemslöjdsfrågor
	Municipality of Bengtsfors
CRAFTMAKERS	Six craft ambassadors

Table 4 - The network activated by UGOT

NETWORK	CBS
ACADEMICS	Students Researchers Professors
MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS	Design Museum Denmark
FESTIVALS AND ASSOCIATIONS	17th Design Theory Paris Workshop
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	The Design Society

Table 5 - The network activated by CBS

NETWORK	UNITOV
ACADEMICS	Students Researchers Professors
MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS	Fondazione Tor Vergata Ministero della Cultura
FESTIVALS AND ASSOCIATIONS	Festivaletteratura
OTHER CREATIVE INDUSTRIES	MOSAIC Project Track4Craft Project
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	Artigianelli - Trento Uniser
POLICY MAKERS	Fondazione Innovazione Urbana Bologna
CRAFTMAKERS	Fieldwork, co-creation-workshop, events

Table 6 - The network activated by UNITOV

NETWORK	FLV
ACADEMICS	Students
MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL INSTITUTIONS	Fondazione Musei Civici
FESTIVALS AND ASSOCIATIONS	Salone dell'Alto Artigianato di Venezia (Comune VE)
CRAFT ASSOCIATIONS	Confartigianato Venezia CNA Venezia Euteknos Innovative Regional network
SMEs	Unisve Seres
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS	Accademia di Belle Arti UIA-Università internazionale dell'arte
POLICY MAKERS	Comune di Venezia
CRAFTMAKERS	Normal activity, courses, workshops, events

Table 7 - The network activated by FLV

8. The Hephaestus strategy

In order to capitalize as much as possible all the results of the research and the different events already organized within the project by the different partners of the consortium, we propose the following strategy:

1. Expand as much as possible the network of contacts related to the craft and cultural heritage sector within each ecosystem;
2. Extend the invitation to other crafters, stakeholders, institutions and policy makers to ensure that each of those that has taken part in past activity is present to the following ones;
3. Organize events outside strictly academic context: museums, craft fairs, schools, associations, cultural events etc.;
4. Involve in local activities and fieldwork all the crafters who express interest in the project;
5. Ensure that the research approach is bottom-up: start a constructive dialogue with all parties so that they can understand the relevant instances and be represented;
6. Give maximum visibility to each ecosystem and their members: through the project's website and social media, but also through workshops and research activities;
7. Organize moments of dialogue with crafters and Craft Ambassadors and involve them in moments of joint work;
8. Organize residences and exchanges between artisans of different ecosystems.

